

pH and Sorption of Dyes on Chemically-pretreated Tin(IV) Oxide

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Chemical-pretreatment and evokement of ion-exchangeable sites on hydrous oxides has been advocated. To investigate the concept, hydrous tin(IV) oxide was prepared by the action of HNO₃ on tin. The resulting oxide (β -form) was treated with aq. NaOH of varying strength and samples having surface phase pH 3.0-11.0 were prepared. Sorption behaviour of two basic dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue and Safranin-T, was investigated under varying conc., time, temp. and desorbents. The sorption is found to be pH-dependent. Predominant ion-exchange behaviour is postulated.

THE development of cation-exchange properties on silica gel and alumina pretreated with NaOH has been observed¹⁻³. Change in the surface behaviour of tin oxide pretreated with alkalis appears to be an unexplored field. It is known that coulombic attraction or repulsion of protons by a charged surface will lead to a surface phase which has a pH different from that of the bulk solution⁴. Snyder⁵ assigned a value of pH of the alumina surface equal to 12. In the present work surface pH of tin oxide samples means surface phase pH, and pH of 1% aq. extract of the sample has been taken as surface pH or surface phase pH. In this study, tin oxide samples of varying pH (3.0-11.0) were prepared and sorption-desorption behaviour of basic dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BB) and Safranin-T (ST), from aq. solutions was investigated under varying concentrations, time and temp.

Treatment of hydrous oxides, like tin oxide, with an amount of alkali insufficient to dissolve them often yields acid salts which are expected to be cation-exchangers, if the cations of the alkali (counter-ion) are not built into the net-work. The net-work of the oxide on treatment with a base may react or coordinate with hydroxide ions, incorporating the diffusible cations (cation-exchanger). Thus, exchange activity would be imparted to the solid through a reversible reaction with the ions in solution, as shown below.

Hence, tin oxide treated with aq. alkali develops negative charge on its surface and with increasing pH the surface acquires increasing negative charge. Thus, high pH may enhance the apparent cation-exchange behaviour of the substrate.

Experimental

Samples of surface phase pH 4.0-11.0, were prepared by treating the β -form of tin oxide (obtained by wet oxidation of the metal with nitric acid) with varying concentrations of NaOH (Table 1). The original sample has surface phase pH 3.0 and particle

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF TIN(IV) OXIDE SAMPLES OF VARYING pH

pH of tin oxide prepared	pH of tin oxide initially taken	Normality of sodium hydroxide solution added (M)	pH of the wash liquid	Preliminary pH of the sample	Surface area* (m ² /g)
4.0	3.0	0.05	3.0	3.8	137 ± 5
4.5	3.0	0.10	3.5	4.4	—
5.0	3.0	0.20	4.0	4.9	139 ± 5
5.5	5.0	0.02	6.0	5.6	—
6.0	5.0	0.05	6.5	6.1	193 ± 5
6.5	6.0	0.01	7.0	6.6	—
7.0	6.0	0.02	7.5	7.1	139 ± 5
7.7	7.0	0.05	8.5	7.9	—
8.0	5.0	0.50	9.0	8.1	150 ± 5
8.5	8.0	0.25	9.5	8.6	—
9.0	8.0	0.50	10.0	9.1	144 ± 5
9.2	9.0	0.10	10.2	9.3	—
9.7	9.0	0.25	10.7	9.9	—
10.0	8.0	1.00	11.0	10.2	135 ± 5
10.2	10.0	0.10	11.2	10.4	—
10.5	8.0	1.50	11.5	10.6	—
11.0	8.0	2.00	12.0	11.1	125 ± 5

* Surface area of tin oxide sample (pH 3.0) = 137 ± 5 m²/g.

size 100-400 mesh. To prepare the samples of different pH the tin oxide sample (100 g), after heating at 110° for 12 hr, was covered separately

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with different concentrations of NaOH (200 ml) at 30°. The samples were kept over-night with occasional shaking. Afterwards, the supernatants were decanted. The solid phase was repeatedly washed with 100 ml portions of distilled water, till the washings had the desired pH (Table 1). A little of the washed sample was dried at 110° for 30 min, and 0.25 g was shaken with water (25 ml) for 30 min, allowed to settle, decanted and pH of the liquid determined. This has been considered as "preliminary pH". Now, the remaining solid was dried at 110° for 12 hr, stored in air-tight amber-coloured bottles and kept in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride. "Systronics" pH-meter (1% accuracy) was used for pH measurements. The results obtained and the conditions followed are shown in Table 1. The surface area (Table 1) of some of the samples were determined by the standard continuous flow method⁶.

The dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BB) (E. Merck) and Safranin-T (ST) (E. Merck) were purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol-water (1 : 1 v/v) mixture and dried at 80° for 24 hr. The homogeneity of the samples was tested chromatographically. AnalaR chemicals and Pyrex/Corning glass apparatus were used. It is known that basic dyes are strongly sorbed by glass. To minimise this effect, all glass-ware were stripped, before use, in cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide solution (1 g/l) for 1 hr and then rinsed with water. CTAB is a surface-active reagent, which is preferentially adsorbed by glass. The above operation was repeated for every experiment.

Procedure :

From the stock solutions in water (1.2712 g/l, BB and 1.4034 g/l, ST), 2.5-100 ml were withdrawn, volume made upto 100 ml (except 100 ml solution) and adsorption was estimated at 630 (BB) and 525 (ST) nm, respectively using "Spekol" spectrophotometer (Carl Zeiss, accuracy $\pm 0.5\%$). The absorbance of ST was not affected by change of pH (pH 4.0-11.0). However, BB changes its colour at pH ≥ 7.0 , which could be restored by sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 4.5). Thus, in all adsorption experiments at pH ≥ 7.0 , the colour of BB was restored by adding acetate buffer (2.0 ml) to the aliquot before colorimetric estimation. Adsorption experiments were conducted by equilibrating tin oxide (0.10 g) with the dye solutions of known concentration in 10 ml volumetric flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat with periodical shaking. After a specified period 2.0 ml was withdrawn from a flask, centrifuged and estimated.

Extent of adsorption vs time :

The variance of adsorption as a function of time (30 min - 72 hr, pH 6.0-11.0) was studied at $30 \pm 1^\circ$, using 4.0, 1.2 and 0.2 m mole/l solutions. It is observed that the process is fast with lower concentrations of the dyes but slow with higher concentrations. Thus, BB (pH 11.0-8.5, 30 min, 4.0 m mole/l) shows 61 to 90% and 81 to 100% adsorption (0.2 m

mole/l). In case of ST (pH 11.0-6.0, 30 min, 4.0 m mole/l), 52 to 80% adsorption is shown, and 77% to almost quantitative adsorption takes place at 0.2 m mole/l. The equilibrium is almost fully attained in 6 hr, although it takes 72 hr (BB) and 24 hr (ST) for higher dye concentrations.

Adsorption vs temperature :

Temperature-variation studies were made at 30-60° with 10 intervals (6 hr) with precision of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ on the substrates of pH 6.0-11.0 (ST) and pH 8.5-11.0 (BB), using the same dye concentrations. The behaviour of the dyes is typical. Thus, in case of BB, the adsorption is almost athermic on substrates of pH 8.5-9.0, while ST shows this behaviour at pH 6.0-8.0. Further, the athermic nature is observed with lower concentrations of the dyes at pH ≥ 9.0 . However, the process appears to be endothermic (30-60°, pH 9.0-11.0, 6 hr) with higher concentrations of the dyes.

The extent of adsorption of solutes normally decreases with rise in temperature. It, however, increases with some dyes⁷. The adsorption, thus, appears to be endothermic. The anomalous adsorption appears to be due to aggregation of the dyes in solution. High temperatures favour the disaggregation of the dye molecules in solution, and it has been suggested⁷ that the dye molecules are reaggregated on adsorption. The large ionic micelles appear to break in the mono-dispersed form by high temperature. The iso-steric heat of adsorption values (Q) are calculated to be 23-80 kJ/mole (BB) and 17-26 kJ/mole (ST).

Adsorption vs pH :

Change in the nature of adsorption with pH (pH 5.0-11.0) is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. pH vs percent adsorption data is shown in Fig. 3. The study reveals that with higher concentrations of BB the adsorption increases with pH (8.5-11.0). There is no adsorption at pH ≤ 8.0 . However, in the concentration range ≤ 1.2 m mole/l the process increases slightly at the above pH range and then decreases to some extent at pH 10.2. Also with lower dye concentrations (1.2-0.1 m mole/l) the adsorption is almost independent of concentration of the dye. The isotherms are of L-type (pH 9.7-11.0) and show maxima in the pH range 9.2-8.5.

In case of ST (Fig. 2), it is observed that the phenomenon increases slowly in the pH range 5.5-8.0, but rapidly in the pH range 8.0-9.2. However, the process decreases in the pH range 9.5-11.0. The maximum adsorption takes place at pH 9.2 (Fig. 3) and drops to zero at pH 4.5. In the pH range 8.5-11.0, the isotherms are of H-type while they are S-shaped at pH ≤ 8.0 .

Adsorption in presence of electrolytes :

The influence of the presence of some strong electrolytes [NaNO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$] on adsorption was also studied. The concentration of the dyes and the electrolytes were

Fig. 1. Change in the nature of adsorption of Brilliant Cresyl Blue from aqueous solutions on tin oxide of varying pH. (Time : 24 hr, Temp. : $30 \pm 1^\circ$)

Fig. 2. Change in the nature of adsorption of Safranin-T from aqueous solutions on tin oxide of varying pH. (Time : 24 hr, Temp. $30 \pm 1^\circ$)

the same i.e., 1.2 and 0.2 m mole/l. It was done with a view to allow the dyes and the cations (Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Al^{3+}) to compete for the adsorption sites. The study reveals that the influence of the cations in respect of the adsorption is in the order $\text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Na}^+$, which probably follows the Shultz-Hardy law in terms of ionic charges. The desorption behaviour of the ions is quite marked with substrates of lower pH. Thus, in presence of

Fig. 3. Change in percentage adsorption of Brilliant Cresyl Blue (O) and Safranin-T (●) with varying pH of tin oxide. (24 hr, $30 \pm 1^\circ$, $d_{ye}_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ moles/litre).

Al(NO₃)₃, BB does not show any affinity for the surface of pH 8.5-9.7 while ST-adsorption decreases considerably. NaNO₃ retards the adsorption to a very small extent.

As stated earlier, the treatment of tin oxide with aq. NaOH develops -ve charge on the surface and also provides exchangeable Na⁺ ions. When adsorption of basic dyes in presence of electrolytes is carried out, the cations (Al³⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Na⁺) compete for the surface, retarding sorption.

Desorption studies :

Desorption of the dyes adsorbed [pH 8.5-11.0 (BB) and pH 6.0-11.0 (ST), 30 ± 1°, 24 hr] from aq. solutions was studied with aq. inorganic electrolytes [0.1 M - 0.001 M NaNO₃, Mg(NO₃)₂, Ba(NO₃)₂ and Al(NO₃)₃]. For this purpose, the dye solutions (250 ml ; 1.2 and 0.4 m mole/l) were equilibrated with the adsorbent (2.5 g), the supernatant decanted, centrifuged and estimated. The solid phase was repeatedly washed with water till the washings were colourless. The washed samples containing adsorbed dyes were dried (80°, 12 hr) and stored.

The sample (0.10 g) loaded with the solute was shaken with aq. electrolytes in 10 ml volumetric flasks. The flasks were immersed in thermostat at 30° and periodically shaken. After 2 hr, 2.0 ml aliquots were withdrawn, centrifuged and estimated.

It is observed that the extent of desorption depends on the nature of the electrolyte, its concentration and pH of the substrate. Thus, the desorption decreases in pH range 8.5-10.5 (BB) and pH 6.0-9.2 (ST). However, it increases with increase in the concentration of NaNO₃. It is maximum with 0.01 M solution of the other electrolytes in the pH

range 8.0-11.0. None of the electrolytes show quantitative desorption. The desorption efficacy of the cations is in the order Ba²⁺ > Mg²⁺ ≈ Al³⁺ > Na⁺.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption behaviour may be presumed to be mainly ion-exchange of the dye-cations (simple or aggregated) with Na⁺ ions on the surface of the substrates. Fig. 4 shows the structures of the dye cations. It has been shown that cationic dyes are aggregated when adsorbed on chromatographic alumina⁸. An estimate of the size of the aggregates of each dye can be made by calculating the coverage factor⁹ (ratio of specific surface area of the substrate estimated from the dye adsorption to the true specific surface area). S, the specific surface area, (m²/g), of a solid is given by the expression¹⁰ :

$$S = Y_m N a \times 10^{-20}$$

where Y_m is the monolayer capacity, N the Avogadro number, and a the cross sectional area of the solute molecule. Taking the values of S (Table 1) and a (144 Å² for BB and 148 Å² for ST), the Y_m values for the dyes at their maximum sorption (pH 11.0 for BB and pH 10.0 for ST) are calculated to be 1.73 × 10⁻⁴ and 1.68 × 10⁻⁴ mole/g, respectively. The maximum amount sorbed (Figs. 1 and 2) is considerably higher than the above calculated values, indicating aggregation of the dyes.

The observations in favour of predominant ion-exchange behaviour are :

- (i) Greater degree of adsorption in a short time interval (lower dye concentrations).
- (ii) Athermic nature of adsorption at lower concentrations of the dyes.

Fig. 4. Structure of the cationic dyes.

The variable heat of adsorption values shows the process to be rather anomalous, indicating that a single reaction may not be responsible for the "Q" values. Dye aggregation process is also exothermic, and it does not explain endothermicity. The endothermic binding may be due to an increase in the number of available sites with temperature as a consequence of dissociation of the dye aggregates in the substrate. This randomization of aggregated chains due to dye-substrate interaction would produce a considerable entropy gain, and this may be the cause coupled with an associated breaking of hydrogen bonds to produce endothermic adsorption.

(iii) The effective desorption of the dyes by inorganic cations (Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Al^{3+}) also point to the ion-exchange nature of the process. Some interaction of the dyes with the substrates are supported by:

- (a) Incomplete desorption with the electrolytes.
- (b) Decrease in the degree of adsorption in the presence of electrolytes.
- (iv) Atomic absorption spectrophotometric studies of the sodium¹¹ present on the substrate before and after adsorption of the dyes show a decrease in sodium content on the substrate at $\text{pH} \geq 8.5$ (BB) and $\text{pH} \geq 6.0$ (ST).

pH and adsorption :

The effect of pretreatment of tin oxide with NaOH is simply to convert the oxide from the H^+ -form to Na^+ -form, and since this form is much lower than the H^+ -form in the ion-selectivity series of oxides and hydrous oxides, displacement of Na^+ ion results in a much more favourable equilibrium than that of the latter ion. Further, the ionically bound sodium content of tin oxide appears to decrease continuously with decreasing pH, becoming essentially negligible in acid range. Thus, the cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the tin oxide samples determined by pH-metric titration method ranges from 0.28 to 1.12 meq. g^{-1} for substrates of pH 6.0-11.0.

At higher pH values, the H^+ ions of the substrate tend to dissociate from the oxygen, leaving a net negative charge on the surface. This will attract the dye-cations. As the pH is lowered, additional H^+ ions may associate with the OH^- , leaving a +ve charge on the surface, as shown below

Thus, the gradual increase in the degree of adsorption with pH [pH 8.5-11.0 (BB) and pH 6.0-9.2 (ST)] may be explained as per eq. (2). In the favourable range of adsorption, the dyes appear to be adsorbed predominantly by ion-exchange, as also indicated by L-type isotherms (pH 9.7-11.0,

BB). H-type isotherms are shown by ST (pH 8.5-11.0). The marked change in adsorption of ST ($\text{pH} > 10.0$ and $\text{pH} < 8.0$) may be due to change in the nature of species to be adsorbed. Change in the nature of species to be adsorbed is indicated by change in the nature of isotherms. The H-type isotherms shown by ST (pH 8.5-11.0) rather assume S-shape at $\text{pH} < 8.0$. Chemisorption and micelle formation can be responsible for the H-type curves, and S-shape represents the case in which it becomes easier for molecules to get adsorbed as adsorption proceeds. Molecules already adsorbed enter into inter-molecular bindings, and assist further adsorption. The species taking part in the adsorption upto $\text{pH} \approx 10.0$ appear to be the cations, and above this pH, the proportion of the cations decreases resulting in the decrease of adsorption. If it is assumed that the alkali is leached out from the oxide surface at high pH values, the alkali ions may compete for the surface, resulting in a decrease of the process. Also, the content of the exchangeable sodium ions on the surface decreases at low pH values, resulting in substrates having no affinity for the dyes (BB, pH 8.0 and ST, pH 4.5).

Isotherms :

The maxima (BB, pH 8.5-9.2) in isotherms may be due to stronger adsorbate-adsorbate and/or solute-solvent interactions in comparison to that of adsorbate-adsorbent interaction. Giles *et al*⁸ also reported maxima in some of the adsorption isotherms of cationic dyes to indicate their association in solution.

Conclusion :

It may thus be concluded that, in general, the cationic dyes are adsorbed by slow ion-exchange of the dye cations (singly or as micelles) with the cations on the surface of tin oxide (Na^+). The study, thus, throws light on the nature of active sites responsible for remarkable adsorption.

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